

**Universities' Governance to Reduce Students' Violence Phenomenon
Against Teachers from a Professors' Point of View
"Case Study: Professors of Economics Faculties in Algerian University"**

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Abstract:

This study aims to highlight and confirm the role of university governance in establishing security and curbing the phenomenon of students' violence against the teaching staff from the viewpoint of professors of faculties of economics in the Algerian university as a study community During the third trio of 2020. The descriptive analytical approach and the case study method are adopted where a random probability sample. The electronic questionnaire according to Likert's five-point scale was also used as a data collection instrument and the SPSS program is used for data analysis. The study reaches many results which are: The presence of a high level of student violence against teachers, with its many manifestations and causes, the absence of good governance, there is a weak inversely correlation between violence and governance.

Keywords: Student Violence; Teaching Staff; University Governance; Educational Security; an Algerian university.

JEL classification codes: I21; I2; I.

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حاكمية الجامعات للحد من ظاهرة العنف الطلابي ضد الهيئة التدريسية من وجهة نظر الأساتذة "دراسة حالة: أساتذة كليات الاقتصاد بالجامعات الجزائرية"

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الملخص:

هدفت الدراسة إلى إبراز دور حاكمية الجامعات في إرساء الأمن والحد من ظاهرة العنف الطلابي ضد الهيئة التدريسية من وجهة نظر أساتذة كليات الاقتصاد بالجامعات الجزائرية خلال الثلاثي الثالث من سنة 2020، باعتماد المنهج الوصفي التحليلي ومنهج دراسة الحالة وكانت عينة الدراسة عشوائية. كما تم استخدام الاستبيان الإلكتروني وأدوات التحليل المناسب والاستعانة ببرنامج SPSS إصدار 22. توصلت الدراسة إلى وجود مستوى مرتفع من العنف الطلابي ضد الهيئة التدريسية مع تعدد مظاهره، أسبابه ومواقفه. يقابله غياب للحاكمية الرشيدة مع وجود ارتباط عكسي ضعيف جدا وذو دلالة إحصائية بين العنف والحاكمية. وقدمت توصيات أهمها إعادة النظر في سياسة القبول الجامعي، التطبيق الصارم لقوانين إرساء الأمن التعليمي القائمة على الجزاء والعقاب. اعتماد الخبرة والكفاءة في تعيين مسؤولي الجامعات على اختلاف مناصبهم، تكثيف الأمن وتوفير أطباء نفسانيين استشاريين لمتابعة الطلبة ذوي السلوك العنيف.

الكلمات المفتاحية: عنف طلابي؛ هيئة تدريسية؛ حاكمية الجامعات؛ أمن تعليمي؛ جامعة جزائرية.

رموز تصنيف JEL: I2; I21.

Introduction

When talking about the development of countries, the prosperity of societies and the development of economies; then the credit goes directly to the universities and the outcomes they achieve. It is the first organization carrying the highest and holiest job ever because it is directly related to the promotion of human thought and enlightenment of its path within the various life fields (family, functional, societal, political and even economic), through the creation of knowledge, its dissemination and the service of societies.

The university considers the professor as its added value and its real capital that increases with use and tends to self-generate. The professor is considered as the first guarantor of the continuity of its activity. The professor's output, research, innovations, inventions and scientific literature are the indicator for measuring the university's efficiency and a criterion for its ranking within the global ranking of universities.

The professor who is respectfully evaluated in the most prestigious universities in the world has not lowered its status in Algerian universities. So, the professor has become subject to irresponsible behaviors, the source of which is an elite who is supposed to be the elite of society represented in the character of the student. The latter has dared to show violence against his/her professor in various educational situations for unacceptable reasons. These violent attitudes are ranging from verbal violence, violence against his private property and the worst one is physical violence.

Because of the raise of this phenomenon, it becomes urgent to consider it to determine its reasons and motives, and to find some radical solutions, either deterrent or containment. Thus, this way, students' violence might be replaced by educational security and behavior discipline.

We can say that university governance is an important strategy that will activate the running of universities and efficiently through the proper application; of its principles of accountability, transparency, responsibility and equality for its various members of the faculty and students. And considering the irresponsible behavior and the violence that the student expresses towards his professors and not the most dangerous manifestations with which many universities have become known, it has become urgent to focus on university governance as an important mechanism that will reduce the phenomenon and reduce its impact.

Problematic

Through the abovementioned presentation, the following question can be raised: What is the role of university governance in establishing security and limiting the phenomenon of student violence against economics faculties in Algerian universities?

In order to understand the aspects of the study the following question and sub-questions can be asked:

- What is the level of student violence against the faculty of economics faculties in Algerian university?
- What is the level of application of university governance to the faculties of economics in Algerian university?
- Is there a statistically significant link between university governance and student violence against the faculties of economics in Algerian university?

Hypothesis

- There is a low level of student violence against the faculty of economics faculties in Algerian university;
- There is a high level of university governance in the faculties of economics in Algerian university;
- There is a statistically significant correlation between university governance and student violence against the faculty of economics faculties in Algerian university.

Importance of the study

The importance of the study comes from the seriousness of the spread and exacerbation of the phenomenon of student violence against the teaching staff in universities, in addition to the repetition of its scenes between universities in general and the Algerian university in particular. So, it has become urgent to delve into such dangerous topics that affect the person of the faculty and for reasons that may be more It is trivial and despicable to be related to the students of knowledge.

Objectives of the study

This study aims to denounce the manifestations of violence in universities that students show against their teachers in the various educational, pedagogical and even administrative situations if the teacher is an administrative official, and to search for the most important causes behind the spread of these irresponsible behaviors, and the solutions that must be taken to limit and reduce their impact.

The theoretical framework of the study

We'll cover it in this component, the theoretical and applied literature.

Literature Review:

- **Study: (Suhair Shaker Seddik and Tala Assem Faik, 2018), Governance of university through the use of staggered approach to strategic decision.**

The study aimed to determine the role that the choice of graded approach plays in the strategic decision in university governance, and the study was conducted on the University of Baghdad and Al-Mustansiriyah. The study found that there were no significant differences between the two universities in terms of the two variables of the study, and confirmed the existence of a statistically significant moral correlation between the listed approach to the strategic decision and university governance, and the presence of a significant impact between the two study variables, and recommended inviting strategic decision makers in the two universities to pay attention to this approach to make Competent decisions. (Seddik & Faik, 2018)

- **Study: (Barakat Sarah and Rahhal Iman, 2018), Extrapolating foreign and Arab experience in applying university governance and analyzing their reality in Algeria.**

The study aimed to extrapolate foreign and Arab experiences in applying university governance and analyze their reality in Algeria, and the study concluded that university governance helps stakeholders participate in formulating and discussing recommendations, monitoring budgets, evaluation and accountability, thus improving The university's outputs, and that there is no general model of governance that fits everyone and choosing a model must be a deliberate decision, and its most important recommendations. It also recommended making radical changes,

on top of which is a review of the levels of the bodies supervising the management of the higher education sector in Algeria in order to properly apply the principles of governance, with the need to activate the role of the student and spark dialogue.(Barakat & Rahhal, 2018)

- **Study: (Khaled Al-Sarayrah, 2009), Reasons of behavior's student violence directed against teachers and administrators in public secondary schools in Jordan.**

The study aimed to determine the reasons for adopting violent behavior on the part of males against teachers and administrators from the point of view of students, teachers and administrators. Political; School reasons; Then the psychological reasons, with significant differences at the level of 0.05 a. Attributed to the variable of the nature of the profession. Paying attention to the quality of the media and what it promotes, developing educational curricula and training teachers and administrators to provide them with efficient communication with the student, following up on the psychology of the student in the classroom and in the family to eliminate the causes of mental disorders.(Al-Sarayrah, 2009)

- **Study: (Kamal Al-Hawamdah, 2007), Student violence at the public and private University of Jordan, from the students 'point of view.**

The study aimed to shed light on the phenomenon of student violence in public and private Jordanian universities from the students 'point of view. The social survey was adopted by sample through the questionnaire and the semi-closed interview. The study concluded that the Student Affairs Deanships constitute A source of disability and harm with the absence of transparency and the reduction of the tasks of student councils and student unions, as well as the absence of a specialist in hearing the concerns of students, and one of the most important recommendations of the study is to reduce the gap between the student and the professor and to occupy his time with research and physical and intellectual activities to fill their vacancy. (Al-Hawamdah, 2007)

Student violence against university faculty

The faculty is represented in the teacher who participates with his students in achieving personal growth that reaches the depths of personality and extends to the way of life (Delliou & al., 2006, p. 94), due to the privacy of its research and human outputs qualified to occupy positions within the needs of the labor market.

The university teacher exercises his teaching function that reflects "the apparent performance he performs during the educational situation which is based on interaction between each teacher and students to the extent that stimulates students' thinking and motivation towards learning"(Shuala & Abdel Aziz, 2000, p. 128). It is: "The set of practices performed during the educational situation with the intention of direct influence on the student's performance to adjust it and facilitate the learning process" (Shuala & Abdel Aziz, 2000, p. 128).

He also exercises the research function that translates into: "Organized human behavior that aims to investigate the validity of an important information or event that illustrates a specific situation or phenomenon or to reach a successful solution to an academic or social problem of interest to the individual and society"(Mohieddin, 1999-2000, p. 107), "It refers to the total of activities that The teacher performs it in order to discover new and useful knowledge, distribute it and store it" (Zaher, 2000, p. 46). This function requires creative capabilities, quality and communication to ensure the presentation of research value and cognitive modernity in addition to accurate scientific methods and sound methods of thinking and directing thought and research towards facts.

As for the administrative position, it has made the teacher the cornerstone of the university organizational structure, which enables him to the university administration and coordination between its units to occupy some positions in it as university president, college dean, head of department and other positions that enable him to run the university's affairs and advance them for the best in the framework of improvement and development for its various administrative levels, within its obligations and within the limits of its responsibilities, in which the student constitutes its first priority.

Within all these sacred tasks that occupy the time and effort of the teacher, we find that he is rewarded within his various teaching positions with irresponsible behaviors of some students that translate into various forms of violence reflecting the absence of the student's value system. Writers and researchers in many fields, psychology and sociology in particular, have been interested in developing definitions of the phenomenon of student violence as: "An intentional voluntary act with the intent to cause harm, damage, or sabotage objects or property, or private or public establishments, civil or governmental, by using force, and violence is a behavioral response characterized by a severe emotional character that may involve a decrease in the level of insight and thinking"(Abu Aneer, 2016, p. 214).

As for university student violence, it refers to: "A group of psychological or physical behaviors that a university student or group of students perform against another student, group of students, or any university body, and includes physical or psychological harm, theft, tampering with others' property or the destruction of university property"(Mayhew, Caldwell, & Goldman, 2011, pp. 253-269), It is "compulsive behavior patterns that include physical abuse, psychological abuse, economic exploitation and property damage by students against ... their teachers at the university"(Elyan, 2014, p. 32).

The causes and the sources of university student violence are varied; their generation varies as "Rabhi Mustafa Elyan" compiled them among factors, the most important of which can be translated in Table N°1:

**Table N°1
Reasons for university student violence against the faculty**

The factors	The reasons
Mental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feeling frustrated as a result of the domineering relationship between the student and the teacher, which makes the student violent in his behavior and reactions to the lecturer. - Suppressing feelings and emotions, which causes the student to breathe about them by force and violence and not accept the other, as well as failing to perform his duties, important if he feels provoked by the teacher or embarrassed during the class. - The depressive symptoms accompanying the student's age in which we experience disturbances in his behavior, poor social sense, indifference to the feelings of others, and failure to abide by rules and laws (he is neither a child nor he a man).
Family, social and economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A history of domestic violence and poor family upbringing; - wrong socialization in the raising of starch; - Repression and frustration resulting from the poor standard of living and social differences among students, which generates a sense of discrimination on the part of the professor and the birth of hatred between them; - Some students are subordinate to their colleagues and imitate their violent behavior

	<p>against teachers;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The spread of tribalism among the students and the student's possession of mediation, which makes him not afraid of punishment for the professor's violence; - The student's belief that his future is unknown and the job market will not accommodate all the students, which makes him not think about his future, and therefore he practices violence against others and his professor.
Cultural	<p>Staying away from religious and moral values, such as opposing female students, cursing or mocking the professor.</p>
University environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Teaching Factors: - Lack of future prospects that stimulate the student, such as the specter of unemployment, economic stagnation, which makes him indifferent to his educational attainment or his behavior with his teachers and colleagues; - Weak academic, psychological and directional counseling by professors to reduce riots; - Focusing on teaching methods on indoctrination and memorization without assigning the student to duties and research that occupy his thinking and emptiness; - The absence of an ethical value message for the teaching profession today, so the professor's relationship with his students has become lacking in values, inclusion and direction (alienation that the student experiences with his teacher); - The absence of academic plans to spread awareness and assume responsibility for the student, by introducing him to all penal and penal laws. ○ Administrative factors: - The absence of a system of monitoring student gathering places; - Leave the university door open to strangers ; - Tolerance of punishing some students for their violent behavior against the professors, and being satisfied with the student's presentation of a graphic apology to his professor ; - The low efficiency of university legislation and regulations and the extent of their implementation; - Weak university security and allowing students to be at the university outside working hours; - The administration's failure to respond to the legitimate requests of students. ○ Student Factors: - Lack of motivation to learn, competition among students, and weak religious and moral standards; - The student's indifference to laws and regulations because they have people to defend them; - The space between the lectures and their lack of engaging in educational and entertainment activities that occupy their free time; - The appearance of students in immodest clothes that may lead to a collision with his professor who rejects such appearances; - The student's freedom to move to other disciplines in the event of failure in a specialization opened the way for them to be indifferent to the existence of many

alternatives;

- The inability to control university inputs (university policy is a right for everyone, and the state follows the quantum policy).

Source: (Elyan, 2014, pp. 44-50, with adaptation)

The most important theories that dealt with the subject of student violence are summarized as follows: (Al-Atoum & Daraghmeh, 2014, p. 223)

- **Psychoanalytic theory:**

The analytical school emphasized the impact of instincts, emotions and imbalances that occur within the student as a human being in the emergence of abnormal and deviant behaviors, as well as various complex and psychological diseases. Analytical theory also interpreted violence directed towards others as a form of aggression with the aim of eliminating pain and obtaining pleasure or self-defense, even if it was at the expense of others.

- **Behavioral theory:**

This theory explains violence in terms of stimulus and response. Skinner indicates that a person learns behavior through reward and punishment. The rewarded behavior of the individual tends to repeat it, and the punished behavior does not repeat it, and this behavior applies to violence and aggression.

- **Biological theory:**

Violence is a result of the biological characteristics of a person, where the increase of some hormones such as the male hormone plays a role in stimulating the motivation towards violence, especially among young people.

- **Social learning theory:**

The owners of this theory assume that people learn violence through observation and imitation of others, and that some social environments may encourage and reinforce violent behavior in order to prevent them from being themselves victims of violence.

- **Frustration theory:**

"Dollard" and "Miller" postulate that individuals in different socioeconomic classes experience significant disappointments; these frustrations create a violent response to the individual's frustration and injustice, Unfortunately, there are many manifestations and forms of violence in which students master their professors, as a result of the many reasons mentioned above, which, no matter how great they are, will not be an excuse for committing such behavior, we present the following:

- **Physical violence:** It takes several forms, the most important are:

- Beating, assault and bodily harm to a professor on or off campus;
- Robbery of the professor's property, either by theft or by cracking;
- Take up the bladed weapon against the professor, Verbal harassment;
- Bad graffiti against the professor, mentioning his name and surname;

- **Moral violence:** It takes several forms, the most important are:

- Insulting the person of the professor;
- Mockery and prejudice against the professor during an educational situation;
- Disobeying and not submitting to the requests and orders of the professor within the educational situation;

- Stirring up chaos and encouraging student revolt against the professor by following the policy of the shepherd and the flock, whereby the shepherd is the student who encourages rebellion and the herd is the group of imitated students who are willing to run the shepherd without thinking.

Universities' Governance

The concept of university governance comes as a response to the crisis that the university has become aware of in terms of corruption, bureaucracy and others, that carry preventive and deterrent solutions through which they aim to activate the university's activities and improve its outputs by applying its principles: transparency, removing all ambiguity, misleading, and clarifying the vision for all parties in it, legal accountability, responsibility and analysis, the ethics of the profession and finally establishing the principle of equality and justice among all parties in the organization. University governance is defined as "an integrated system represented in the set of laws, regulations, and instructions aimed at achieving the quality and distinction of operations and outputs, and the academic; and administrative departments, by choosing appropriate and effective strategies to achieve the university's goals" (Nasereddin, 2019).

The rational governance of universities requires that the university work to create and form a board of trustees whose members are chosen with precision and wisdom, who have long experience in the academic field, who are distinguished by integrity and conscientiousness, and who are not bound by private interests, as they are assigned tasks that will spread university security and limit the different manifestations of student violence, as this council performs the following tasks: (Nawasrah, 2012, pp. 43-44)

- Drawing up the general policy according to the requirements of the public interest and the university's interest, where it is necessary to focus on the university admission policy and determine the number of admissions and the like, with the inclusion of the moral and ethical dimension of the student within the conditions;
- Laying down the university's laws, regulations and instructions that regulate students' behavior with the faculty in the form of a penalty and punishment;
- Selection and appointment of university presidents and their deputies, deans of colleges, institutes, scientific centers.... on the basis of experience and competence not on the basis of private interests and favoritism;
- Drawing up a policy for scientific research and allocating the necessary allocations for it within the university budget; Establishing quality standards in academic education;
- Separation of students who commit acts of violence and violations.

The application of the rational governance of universities requires the building of two approaches that will reduce and limit the manifestations of student violence in universities, as the two approaches contain: (The Authenticity and Modernity Team, 2010, pp. 4-5)

- **Preventive approach:**

- Focusing on the curriculum in its educational aspect by including the academic subjects with a set of lofty values such as tolerance, dialogue, acceptance of difference, and awareness of rights and duties;
- Initiate the preparation of a charter that includes the rights and duties of all parties within each institution separately. The purpose of this charter is to define the responsibilities of all actors in the educational system;

- Finding a mediation mechanism in all university institutions that contributes to dialogue, easing tensions, and reducing the amount of aggressive behavior;
 - Establishing partnerships with public authorities (National Security, Auxiliary Forces, Gendarmerie, Ministry of Justice) to organize patrols and outreach campaigns to eliminate violence in the vicinity of educational institutions;
 - Deepening the sense of belonging to the school and the values of respect for its surroundings, by imposing the generalization of wearing school uniforms by pupils inside primary schools with the support of the Ministry;
 - Organizing various cultural, artistic and sporting events at the local and regional levels concerned with the rejection of violence, consolidating the values of citizenship and civic behavior spreading mobilization around them, and highlighting their importance in the educational milieu in particular and within society in general;
 - Creating educational clubs in all educational institutions that enable students to fill their free time, make them aware of the issues they are concerned with.
- **Security approach:**
 - Organizing extensive awareness-raising campaigns to introduce the phenomenon of violence, its forms and negative effects at all levels, and activate the mechanisms available to monitor violations and take the necessary measures to make the educational institutions;
 - Academies contract with private companies to guard educational institutions and ensure their protection; Coordination and cooperation with the Ministry of the Interior in order to provide security in the vicinity of our educational institutions.

Practical Study

Through this element, we will try to project what is theoretical to reality.

Study Approach

The descriptive and analytical approach is adopted through a Search in references and books to view the theoretical and field studies on the subject. As for the field study, we depend on the sampling method through which an electronic questionnaire is designed to electronically collect data for professors of faculties of economics in Algerian university. In addition, appropriate analysis instruments are adopted to analyze the collected data and test. The assumptions are tested by the SPSS version 22. Then, the results of the statistical analysis are analyzed and explained.

Study population and sample

The study population is all the professors of economics faculties in Algerian university. As for the study sample, it is a random probability sample in which an electronic questionnaire is designed and distributed to professors of economics faculties in Algerian university via social media and personal emails. 246 valid questionnaires are collected for the study.

The study instrument

The electronic questionnaire is adopted as a instrument for data collection. It is designed in a simple way that allows the respondent reply without much time and effort wasting. This questionnaire is divided into three sections:

- The first section: General data about the interrogators;
- The second section: Items that reflect the reality and level of student violence in faculties of economics in Algerian university (dependent variable);
- The third section: Items that reflect the reality and level of university governance in the faculties of economics in Algerian university (the independent variable).

In order to ensure the content validity, the questionnaire is distributed for arbitration by professors specialized in business administration and management of human resources. For the reliability of the study instrument, the coefficient of the study is calculated for the alpha Crumbath coefficient for the questionnaire axes, Total coefficient reached 73.5 % (**look Appendix: Table N° 1**).

Discuss the results of study

• Characteristics of the study sample

Through the analysis of the retrieved questionnaires, it is found that the number of females (132) rating by 53.7% is approximately similar to male's number (114) rating by 46.3 % (**see Appendix: Table N° 2**). This demonstrates the university's fairness in employing male and female genders. As for the civil status, the majority (166) is married, rating by 67.5%, (**see Appendix: Table N° 3**). This reflects the social stability of the majority of the respondents, and this has an impact on psychological balance, the ability to deal with students in various educational situations, as well as family obligations that make them more adhere to their work positions. Concerning ages, the majority of respondents belong to the category (30 to 50 years) by (213) rating by 86.6%. Most professors are from the youth category who are active in science and scientific research, as their research activity increases from preparing the doctoral thesis, the university qualifications and the professorship file (**see Appendix: Table N° 4**). As for seniority, the distribution is close between three groups, as the majority belongs to the category (from 10-15 years) rating by 30.5%. Then, the second category (less than 5 years) rating by 24.8%, and the final category (from 5 to less than 10 years) rating by 24% (**see Appendix: Table N° 5**).

The previous characteristics reflect that the colleges under study have diverse teaching competencies, with acceptable field experience that allows achieving the efficiency of university performance, provided that most of the professors have experience in teaching and dealing with students, and the door to employment is open to new doctors, and most of them are engaged in scientific research for the purpose of discussing their theses and promotion to higher ranks (qualification and professorship).

• Explanation of the results related to the axis of student violence

The first hypothesis states: **There is a low level of student violence against the professors of economics faculties in Algerian university**; It is found from the respondents' answers about the statements of student violence dealing with three dimensions that the dimension of the manifestations of student violence with an arithmetic mean is (3.517) and a standard deviation of (0.88) (**see Appendix: Table N° 6**), where the dimension tends to approve, except for the phrase that reads: The assault was by breaking the teacher's property, the answers tended to be neutral, and the phrase: The assault was by stealing the professor's property (a computer), the answers tended to disagree. The dimension of the causes of student violence with an arithmetic mean (4.119), and a standard deviation (0.544) (**see Appendix: Table N° 6**), the dimension tends to agree. Finally, the dimension of student violence situations with an arithmetic mean (3.937) and a standard deviation (0.666), (**see Appendix: Table N° 6**), the dimension tends to agree. The total arithmetic mean of the axis of student violence as a whole is (3,858) and a standard deviation

(0.533), (see Appendix N° 6), the respondents' answers on the axis of violence tend to agree. This indicates the existence of various manifestations of student violence against the faculty. The respondents either exposed or heard about student violence and its manifestations varying between verbal and physical attacks, the breaking of university property. The violence is within the university walls, except for breaking the professor's property which is neutral. The causes of violence varied from the lack of security, the absence of some religious values, psychological disturbances, the absence of some moral values, the concentration of university entrance that focuses on quantity over the quantity, the students' imitation of their colleagues as a matter of manhood. these reasons are consistent with the results of the study (**Khaled Al-Sarayra, 2009**), where the reasons range from political, scholastic and psychological. The professors are exposed to student's violence in faculties of economics during teaching period, examination period when the results are announced, in the consultation and finally in the final deliberations. **All these prove the first hypothesis.**

- **Explanation of the results related to the axis of University governance**

The second hypothesis states: **There is a high level of university governance in the faculties of economics in Algerian university**; it is found from the respondents' answers about the statements of University's governance that deals with two dimensions: The dimension of the university's efforts to establish governance with an arithmetic mean (2.367) and a standard deviation (0.607). (see **Appendix: Table N° 7**) where the answers tend to disagree, except for the phrase that states: The university introduces students to the various laws that govern their behavior and define their rights and duties towards their professors; the answers are neutral. For the professor's efforts dimension, with an arithmetic mean (2,184) and a standard deviation (0.719), it tends to disagree. (See **Appendix: Table N° 7**). The governance axis also tends to disagree with an arithmetic mean (2.275) and a deviation (0.452) (see **Appendix: Table N° 7**) where the respondents unanimously agree that the university does not make an effort to effectively establish the principles of university governance of transparency, fairness, responsibility and accountability; and it does not take it in consideration the ethical dimension of selection (lack of justice and transparency), it does not provide adequate security that is constantly present next to student gatherings, it does not exercise punishment and punish abused students, especially expulsion that must be subject to the spread of administrative corruption, including favoritism and favoritism for some students, which causes them to neglect the professors' reports filed against the battered student. The professor also does not make an effort to achieve psychological balance during the student's violence and uses the same method, and there is an excessive friction with the student, and the student's anger is neither absorbed nor contained during a violent situation, and there are no manifestations of justice in dealings with the students. Neither the university practices the legal security and preventive approach, nor does the professor practice the inclusive approach. **The second hypothesis is not verified.**

- **Explanation of the results related to the axis of the relationship between university governance and student violence**

The third hypothesis states: **There is a statistically significant correlation between university governance and student violence against the faculty of economics faculties in Algerian university**, The correlation coefficient between the axis of university governance and student violence is (-0.164) at a significant level (Sig = 0.01) which is a very weak inverse correlation, but it is statistically significant. Whereas the relationship between the two variables is based on the fact that the more universities are governed, the less violence is spread and vice versa. The results of the study show that there is student violence against the faculty with an absence of university governance what makes the relationship between them weak. We explain

that by the absence of good governance in the colleges under study, where their principles remain ink on paper, far from actual application. **This reflects the fulfillment of the third hypothesis.**

Conclusion

Student's violence against the faculty members is one of the most dangerous manifestations that have escalated in the Algerian university and it has many manifestations from material to moral violence. Its position has increased in terms of examination, reconsideration, deliberations, during the lesson, etc., and its causes have abounded in terms of political (the policy of prevention for university entrance that focuses on quantity without gender), Academic (the absence of actual application of deterrent, punitive, and security laws as well as containment), and psychological (blind imitation, psychological pressure, counseling masculinity in a misplaced place). Thus, university governance becomes an important mechanism that helps the rational application of its principles to reduce and limit the manifestations of this phenomenon.

Results of the study:

The study reached a set of results, the most important ones are:

- The existence of a high level of student's violence against the faculty of the Faculties of Economics at the Algerian University, with its many manifestations, causes and instances;
- The existence of a very weak level that tends to lack governance in economics faculties in Algerian university;
- The existence of a very weak and statistically significant reverse correlation between student violence against the teaching staff and university governance to establish educational security in economics faculties in the Algerian university;
- Governance principles remain ink on paper, the fact that contributed to the absence of rational governance in economic faculties in Algerian university;
- The absence of preventive solutions to curb the phenomenon of violence.

Recommendations

- The necessity of a strict implementation of the laws to establish educational security which stipulates the dismissal of students who practice violence against the faculty and govern their dealings with the teaching staff in the form of punishment and punishment, and to amend them according to the circumstances and changes therein;
- The necessity for developing a general policy based on what is required by the interest of the university and the public interest, especially the university admission policy by shifting towards focusing on the type of students (with good grades) and conditioned by the moral and ethical dimension;
- Adopting experience and competence in appointing university officials, such as: university president, dean, head of department, etc. A basis for choice and not favoritism, to ensure educational security, eliminate all forms of violence and corruption, and achieve good governance;

- Expelling students who carry out acts of violence, irregularities and riots, especially against the teaching staff;
- Familiarizing the student with his rights and duties and informing him of the various laws, particularly penalties;
- Opening the door to dialogue among the administration, the professor and the student, to reduce tension and the amount of aggressive behavior;
- Subject professors to training courses on how to deal with students within different educational situations in order to establish the proper professional behavior of the professor and make him a model for the strict and discursive professor who is punished and understood;
- Providing consultant psychiatrists to guide students with violent behavior and try to address its causes;
- Intensifying security in the university while ensuring its spread in student gathering places within the educational situations especially exams;
- Establishing partnerships with public authorities, such as National Security, to organize awareness campaigns to eliminate violence in university settings;
- Organizing cultural and sporting events denouncing violence and calling for the consolidation of students' values of citizenship and responsible behavior;
- Intensifying cultural activities, sports, entertainment and scientific activities to occupy students' spare time.

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Appendix

**Table N°1
Test of reliability**

Reliability statistics	
Cronbach's alpha	Number of elements
,735	32

Source: Preparing researchers to adopt the outputs of the SPSS program.

**Table N°2
Distribution of the study sample according to the gender variable**

Sex					
		Frequency	percentage	Frequency Valid	Cumulative percentage
Valid e	Man	114	46,3	46,3	46,3
	Woman	132	53,7	53,7	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Source: Preparing researchers to adopt the outputs of the SPSS program.

Table N°3
Distribution of the study sample according to the civil status

Civil status					
		Frequency	percentage	Frequency Valid	Cumulative percentage
Valide	Married	166	67,5	67,5	67,5
	Unmarried	79	32,1	32,1	99,6
	devoured	1	,4	,4	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Source: Preparing researchers to adopt the outputs of the SPSS program.

Table N°4
Distribution of the study sample according to the age variable

Civil status					
		Frequency	percentage	Frequency Valid	Cumulative percentage
Valide	Lessthan30 yearsold	166	67,5	67,5	67,5
	Between30 and 50 yearsold	79	32,1	32,1	99,6
	More than50 yearsold	1	,4	,4	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Source: Preparing researchers to adopt the outputs of the SPSS program.

Table N°5
Distribution of the study sample according to the seniority variable

Seniority in teaching					
		Frequency	percentage	Frequency Valid	Cumulative percentage
Valid e	Lessthan 5 years	61	24,8	24,8	24,8
	Between 5 and 10 years	59	24,0	24,0	48,8
	Between 10 and 15 years	75	30,5	30,5	79,3
	Between 15 and 20 years	34	13,8	13,8	93,1
	More than 20 years	17	6,9	6,9	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Source: Preparing researchers to adopt the outputs of the SPSS program.

Table N°6
Manifestations of student violence against professors

Descriptive statistics					
	N	Min	Max	Moy.	Ecart type
You have been attacked by a student, or you have seen or heard about an assault on a colleague	246	1	5	4,14	1,052
The abuse witnessed or heard about the professor was insulting and using bad language	246	1	5	4,13	1,060

You were subjected to beating and violation of the sanctity of your body	246	1	5	3,36	1,347
The assault was by breaking the professor's property	246	1	5	2,98	1,334
The assault was by crushing university property	246	1	5	3,26	1,382
The assault was on campus	246	1	5	4,16	1,109
The assault was to steal the professor's property (for example, a computer)	246	1	5	2,59	1,221
Manifestations of student violence against professors	246	1,00	5,00	3,5174	,88006
Lack of guard and security at the university	246	1	5	4,01	1,169
The absence of religious values for some students	246	1	5	4,27	,940
The student suffers from mental disorders	246	1	5	3,76	,982
The absence of moral values among some students	246	1	5	4,52	,721
Lack of proper selection of university enrollees due to the state's policy of student quantities and education for all	246	0	5	4,38	,934
Imitation of the student to his colleagues in blaming the professor as a matter of manhood	246	1	5	3,77	,894
The absence of punishment and deterrent measures against manifestations of student violence	246	1	5	4,46	,821
Excessive or negligent contact between the professor and the student	246	1	5	3,79	1,059
Causes of student violence against the faculty	246	1,88	5,00	4,1199	,54443
The prestige of some professors is weak, making them vulnerable to violence	246	1	5	3,52	1,029
During the examination and guard period (preventing the student from cheating)	246	1	5	4,68	,655
Exposure to violence during the announcement of student evaluation points	246	1	5	3,98	,979
Exposure to violence while re-examining the possibility of an error in correcting the student's paper	246	1	5	3,81	,984
Exposure to violence after final deliberations and the announcement of the student's success or failure	246	1	5	3,69	1,047
Educational situations in which the professor is exposed to violence from his students	246	1,00	5,00	3,9374	,66699
The dependent variable: student violence	246	1,48	5,00	3,8582	,53383
N valide (liste)	246				

Source: Preparing researchers to adopt the outputs of the SPSS program.

Table N°7

The respondents of the study sample about the university governance variable according to each dimension the all the axis

Statistiques descriptives					
	N	Min	Max	Moy.	Ecart type
The university takes the student's moral dimension into account in the university's admission requirements	246	1	5	1,72	,705
The university provides security personnel who are constantly	246	1	5	2,35	1,198

present near students and student gatherings					
The university introduces students to the various laws that govern their behavior and define their rights and duties towards their professors	246	1	5	3,26	1,348
The university is working to punish students who incite and instigate college riots	246	1	5	2,91	,914
The university provides consultant doctors for students who exhibit violent behavior against their professors	246	1	5	1,96	,960
The university is working to punish the student who violates his professor with a final parcel	246	1	5	2,14	1,114
The university takes seriously the reports that professors raise against students who exhibit violent behavior against their professors.	246	1	5	2,24	,696
Establishing educational security through the university's efforts	246	1,00	5,00	2,3670	,60708
The teacher maintains his balance while the student tries to encroach him in an educational situation and does not use the same style as the student	246	1	5	2,08	,916
The professor leaves a distance in his dealings with his students that makes the professor a professor and the student a student.	246	1	5	1,93	,962
The teacher works to absorb the student's anger into his violent behavior and contain him instead of punishing him	246	1	5	2,39	1,043
The professor works to help students solve their personal problems	246	1	5	2,56	1,059
The professor practices justice with his students in various educational situations	246	1	5	1,97	1,072
Establishing educational security through the efforts of the professor	246	1,00	4,80	2,1846	,71981
Independent variable: university governance	246	1,00	4,90	2,2758	,45204
N valide (liste)	246				

Source: Preparing researchers to adopt the outputs of the SPSS program.

Table N°8

Correlation coefficient to test the existence of a relationship between university governance and student violence

		The dependent variable: Student violence	Independent variable: University governance
The dependent variable: Student violence	Corrélation de Pearson	1	-,164**
	Sig. (bilatérale)		,010
	N	246	246
Independent variable: University governance	Corrélation de Pearson	-,164**	1
	Sig. (bilatérale)	,010	
	N	246	246

** . La corrélation est significative au niveau 0.01 (bilatéral).

Source: Preparing researchers to adopt the outputs of the SPSS program.